

Technical Cost Reduction for 3.6L V6 Engine Piston & Rings: A Case Study

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Abstract

This paper reviews the feasibility in a technical cost-reduction program to make significant changes in engine piston components. These changes had proposed eliminating anodizing on top ring grooves of the pistons, changing the design of the second ring from micro-Napier to nano-Napier, and eliminating chrome plating. A full benchmarking process was run, and a Proof-of-Concept testing procedure was developed to verify if the changes encode the feasibilities. Reliability and performance from the proposed solutions are subject to rigorous dyno testing. It conducted a detailed DFMEA and DVPR assessment to ensure a proper foundation for the validation of proposed cost-saving measures in keeping the quality and integrity with respect to engine components.

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Keywords: Technical cost reduction, Engine piston components, Anodizing removal, Piston top ring groove, Micro-Napier to nano-Napier design, Chrome plating removal, Benchmarking process, Proof of Concept (POC) testing, Dynamometer (dyno) testing, Dependability and performance, Design Failure Mode, and Effects Analysis (DFMEA), Design Verification Plan and Report (DVPR), Cost-saving measures, Engine component quality and integrity

1. Introduction

This study estimated the feasibility for cost reduction in a 3.6 L V6 engine design by modifying some of the main components of the engine. This research evaluated the feasibility of eliminating anodizing on the piston top-ring groove, transitioning to nano-Napier from micro-Napier for the second ring design, and eliminating chrome plating. These proposed changes were very carefully evaluated with a spate of tests, from Proof of Concept down to lengthy dynamometer tests and rigorous Design Failure Mode and Effects Analysis or DFMEA and Design Verification Plan and Report or DVPR, in order not to see the performance of the reliability of the engine compromised by these changes. Any new product development program must comprise projects focused on product cost reduction and customer value enhancement because competitiveness is forcing customers to ask for more quality and functionality in a new product without price increases [1].

2. Literature Review

Barrell, et al. [2] conducted research on the influence and sliding wear of a gasoline engine top piston ring groove. Their work brought out an important factor of anodizing, which avoids micro welding or surface damage. According to their results, breaking anodizing would link to high wear, mainly challenging cost reduction efforts within the engine design process. Wong and Tung [3] reviewed these trends on reduction of friction in the internal combustion engine. The role of surface treatment could be seen with effects of material technologies and additives in lubricants. Their review, therefore, shows that advanced coatings and material modifications play a very important role in improving engine efficiency to future levels to meet modern-day environmental standards on reduced emissions. Meikandaset al. [4] investigated the tribological behavior of anodized pistons, analyzing their tribological behavior using soft and hard anodizing and micro-arc oxidation. The results indicate that each of these anodizing techniques provides wear resistance differently, impinging on component life

under different operational conditions connected with the performance of engine components. Ronen, Etsion, and Kligerman [5] provided a model of fractional friction reduction in reciprocating automotive components due to proper micro-surface structures. The results of the mentioned research proved that texturing of the surface can retain hydrodynamic effects even with nominally parallel surfaces, and it can reduce frictional losses to a large extent, which is very important for improvement in engine efficiency. Goni et al. [6] addressed the development of high-performance automotive components using new aluminum-based composites. Their work was targeted at whether these composites could be used for pistons, thus giving value to reduction in weight and improvement in wear behavior apart from raising thermal conductivity parameters regarded as critical for developing cost-effective, high-performance engine components.

Caputo et al. [7] made a study on using anodized aluminum as a thermal barrier coating for diesel engine pistons. Their research showed that while the coating reduced fuel consumption and heat transfer, it created very small inefficiencies related to the roughness of this coating, hence impacting overall engine performance. Picas et al. [8] Compare high velocity oxy fuel coatings over traditional hard chrome plating for pistons and valves. Results show that HVOF coatings have very good mechanical and tribological properties; thus, they can be a good substitute for chrome, especially in applications of environmental concern. Ma et al. [9] investigated the tribological performance and scuffing behaviors of different piston ring coatings against a chrome-plated cylinder liner. Their results have shown that diamond-like coatings exert very good friction and wear properties at higher temperatures, which recommend them for high-performance engine applications. Gnanavel et al. [10] examined the feasibility of various coated steel pistons as an alternate material instead of aluminum alloy pistons for small engines. In their work, it was reported that the steel pistons were more cost-effective, had improved strength, and superior thermal performance, making them applicable for higher durability in some uses. Pacana et al. [11] applied the control chart to monitor and improve the quality of the anodizing process for aluminum pistons. In their research, it is noticed that tools of quality management enable identification and solving problems in the process of anodizing to increase reliability and repeatability of the process undertaken for making pistons. Rayate [12] discusses scuffing resistance in the piston pin bores, putting much emphasis on optimum clearance and surface treatments for improvement in durability without compromising cost. Such a focus on minimizing scuffing through precision engineering could be an influence on cost-effective design strategies for high-performance pistons. The importance of surface finish and lubrication practices is clearly brought out by the work of Rayate [13], who investigated pin tick noise and bushing wear in heavy-duty engines. He was able to show that under poor lubrication and incorrect piston pin surface finish, a great deal of wear takes place and that improvements should be made in an engineering like manner for improved component performance and life. This is the kind of insight that is needed at the hub of technical cost reduction strategies to ensure that changes do not compromise reliability in engine components.

3. Top Ring Anodizing Removal

3.1 Design Analysis

The technical change proposed for the test is eliminating the hard anodized layer placed on the flank of the first ring groove in a piston. Generally, this consists of mainly improving wear resistances. The proposal itself therefore raises some immediate misgivings, several of which require very close check. The first is that the anodizing layer helps in resisting normal engine operation, thus preventing extra wear in the highest ring groove. The removal of this layer can result in accelerated wear and possibly shorter service life. Second, micro-welding—tending to occur by metal particles bonding to the groove surface—might be increased in the absence of the protective anodized coating, which will result in functional failure. Finally, it can also risk ring groove pounding out where the ring groove is acted upon by forces of impact from the piston ring, which helps to relieve the hard-anodized layer. Each one of these issues must be addressed with stringent testing to ensure that the removal of anodizing does not compromise the functionality of the piston and duration of the piston.

Figure 1: Piston with top ring anodizing layer

Figure 2: Piston with no anodizing layer

3.2 POC Test – Top Ring Groove Comparison

The results of comparative testing for the pistons with hard anodizing (HA) and without anodizing prove both their effectiveness for contact properties improvement [14]. The wear on a groove was almost strictly limited to the top ring, and it was recognized to be acceptable after continuous operations of 200 running hours at peak power, in comparison to the pistons without cooling jets. Wear data here are assumed to be presented for the worst-case scenario, and it concludes that even under these conditions, the piston ring groove does not wear beyond the preset thresholds of performance and endurance.

Figure 3: Piston top ring groove wear under peak power cycle

3.3 POC Test – Temperature Analysis with Temp Plug

During the thermal testing carried out with the hard-anodized (HA) piston, the average temperature measured in the first ring groove was 241 °F, with a standard deviation of 10.3 °F. These temperatures are well below the maximum limit of 300 °F, which opens potential avenues for examining alternatives to HA coatings. These data imply the presence of a buffer in the thermal performance, which could be beneficial for exploring non-HA coatings. This margin of error may provide a chance to decrease expenses or modify manufacturing processes without compromising the thermal endurance of the piston.

Location	Cyl 1	Cyl 2	Cyl 3	Cyl 4	Cyl 5	Cyl 6	Avg	StDev
	Temp 10R	Temp 3L	Temp 8R	Temp 5L	Temp 9R	Temp 2L		
1 Center Top Land	266	253	270	260	260	261	261.7	5.8
2 Center Top Land	281	237	261	248	270	252	258.2	15.9
3 Center Top Land	271	278	261	268	260	272	268.3	6.9
4 Center Top Land	248	256	249	256	234	261	250.7	9.5
5 Behind Top Groove	245	239	253	239	248	246	245.0	5.4
6 Behind Top Groove	249	236	234	229	254	229	238.5	10.6
7 Behind Top Groove	246		241	250	257	254	249.6	6.3
8 Behind Top Groove	222	244	229	238	218	245	232.7	11.4
9 Above Pin Hole front	220	214	226	214	232	209	219.2	8.6
10 Above Pin Hole rear		220	223	226	230	226	225.0	3.7
11 Center Under Crown	254	251	253	235	248	246	247.8	7.0

Table 1: Piston temperature results

3.4 Benchmarking

Benchmark testing of comprehensive wear, pound out, and micro-welding demonstrates that anodizing provides protection against micro-welding at temperatures up to 290°C. However, without anodizing, this protection is significantly reduced, offering protection only up to 255°C. Given that the peak power operations reach temperatures close to 251°C, the margin for top-groove protection is narrow. It is evident that operation without anodizing pushes the piston material to its protective limit.

Figure 4: Benchmarking for wear, pound out and micro-welding

By benchmarking and analyzing competitor engines of similar bore, stroke, specific power outputs, and top-land heights, it is realized that none of them make use of a hard anodizing layer for top-ring groove protection. Such observation gives an indication that this can be an industry trend to resort to other methods or materials which could, on their own accord, provide sufficient durability and wear resistance without the HA layer. The benchmarking process also identifies the different techniques in use within the sector, such methods could provide opportunities for novelty in engine design and cost reduction for protection of critical components [15].

	1.8L Honda HR-V	3.5L Honda Accord	3.7L Lincoln MKZ	5.0L Kia K900	3.6L
Groove Protection	None	None	None	None	Hard Anodized
Engine Configuration	I4	V6	V6	V8	V6
Bore x Stroke (mm)	81.0 mm Bore 87.3 mm Stroke	89.0 mm Bore 93.0 mm Stroke	95.5 mm Bore 86.7 mm Stroke	96.0 mm Bore 87.0 mm Stroke	96.0 mm Bore 83.0 mm Stroke
Specific Power (kW/L)	58.41 kW/L	59.74 kW/L	59.98 kW/L	62.64 kW/L	64.4 kW/L
Top Land Height (mm)	6.34 mm	5.25 mm	5.25 mm	5.15 mm	5.30 mm

Table 2: Piston benchmarking with competitor engine

It is discovered that multiple benchmarking that is focused on power output, peak cylinder pressure, top land height, and thermal load demonstrates that the 3.6 L engine is operated within the threshold of not requiring an anodizing layer for first-rate ring groove safety. That means HA can be eliminated for this class of overall engine performance without the loss of any engine integrity or total performance. The results present a 3.6 L in one single location where normal HA protection could be optional, so there can be negotiations regarding the use of cloth and its cost efficiency.

Figure 5: Benchmarking with specific output and peak cylinder pressure

Figure 6: Benchmarking with power output and top land height

Figure 7: Benchmarking with thermal load and peak firing pressure

Figure 8: Benchmarking with specific power and top land height

These tests include detailed design analysis and exploratory proof of concept (POC) testing of the top ring groove based on detailed temperature measurements, which can significantly enhance confidence in exploring non-HA technical cost reductions. Especially when this is borne out by multiple benchmarks over a wide range of design parameters, it makes the case for investigating a non-hard anodized top-ring groove application. This is particularly important in the identification of cost optimization opportunities at the manufacturing-process level, where economical alternatives to traditional HA can be posited without compromising engine performance or durability.

3.5 DFMEA

A well-thorough Design Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (DFMEA) for the piston would then be the critical requirement in encouraging the use of a non-hard-anodized top-ring-groove piston[16]. This would give detailed information on possible failure modes, the effects of failures, design controls, detection, and the validation involved in making a seamless transition to the non-HA alternative. These areas must be fully addressed to ensure practical, effective implementation of any non-HA alternative.

Potential Failure Mode	Potential Effects of failure	Sev	Potential cause of failure	Occ	Current Design Controls-Detection	Det	RPN
Excessive wear of groove flanks (1st groove)	Smoke from Tail Pipe (5) High Oil Consumption (6) Lack of Performance (6) Increased emissions (10)	10	Insufficient strength of flanks for present mechanical and thermal loads	3	Dynamometer durability testing: DTS(Deep Thermal Shock Test), GED (Gasoline Engine Durability Test), FEE(Fire Engine Endurance Test), ERS (Engine Resonance Survey Test), and PT2TRANS. Vehicle durability testing: PT2/3.	2	60
		10	Ring Groove axial clearance too large (ring flutter)	2		3	60
		10	Piston skirt clearance too large	7		3	210
		10	Due to foreign particles (ingestion)	3		4	120
		10	Top land profile not optimum	3		3	90
		10	Alternate fuel lubricity	4		3	120
		10	Ring Groove axial clearance for present mechanical and thermal loads too small	3		2	60
Ring sticking (1st,2nd groove)							

Table 3: Piston DFMEA for non-HA

It was identified through the DFMEA process that the most critical failures that could result are excessive wear in the ring groove and sticking of the ring, with corresponding critical consequences such as emission of smoke from the tailpipe, increased consumption of oil, decreased performance of the engine, and heightened emissions. The failures can be due to many reasons such as flanks that are relatively weak and incapable of withstanding the current mechanical and thermal loads; poor ring groove axial clearance, which may lead to ring flutter; or nonoptimal top land profiles. On the other hand, the introduction of foreign particles and variations in the lubricity of fuel have also been identified. These failure points had high severity ratings, and overall, the Risk Priority Number (RPN) scores were large, hence indicating that this refinement should be addressed at the design phase and validation.

3.6 DVPR

To prevent wear and detect any potential issues, a range of tests is recommended, such as general durability assessments, peak power evaluations, and scuff resistance trials. The use of Lubrisense steady-state and transient tests for dyno-test engines has been suggested to diagnose oil consumption problems. Moreover, it was advised to conduct vehicle testing under standardized city and highway driving cycles to confirm that the vehicle-level oil consumption is not adversely impacted. These measures were implemented to ensure comprehensive detection and protection against wear-related failures.

4. Napier Change & Chrome Removal

4.1 Design Analysis

The introduction of the Nano Napier shape for the second ring successfully eliminated the need for an outer diameter (OD) grinding operation. This innovation, utilizing raw ring material in the Nano Napier shape, streamlines the production processes. Currently, Nano Napier rings are manufactured and integrated into various customer programs, reflecting a shift towards more efficient production techniques in ring manufacturing.

Figure 9: Current Design (Micro-Napier) Vs. Proposed Design (Nano Napier)

The discontinuation of chrome plating or flashing of the second ring occurs after comprehensive durability testing, which has consistently indicated minimal ring wear, negating the necessity for chrome plating [17]. Traditionally, flash chrome has been utilized in turbocharged or direct injection (DI) applications to enhance wear resistance; however, recent findings suggest that under certain conditions, this additional layer may not be essential for maintaining ring integrity and performance.

4.2 POC Test – Radiometric Oil Consumption & Blowby

In a comparative analysis designed to assess oil consumption and blow-by, a Proof of Concept (POC) test was conducted between the micro-Napier and nano Napier rings. The results demonstrated that the engine set equipped with nano Napier non-chrome rings exhibited improved oil consumption and blow-by across all evaluated categories when compared to the current production micro-Napier rings. This finding indicates the potential of nano Napier rings to enhance engine efficiency and performance.

Test	Oil Consumption				Blowby
	Low Speed Steady State (SSOC)	High Speed Steady State (SSOC)	Overall Steady State (SSOC)	Transient Average	Average
	Grams/Hr (Lbs/Hr)	Grams/Hr (Lbs/Hr)	Grams/Hr (Lbs/Hr)	Grams/Hr (Lbs/Hr)	SCFM (LPM)
J3022 Test 1 Baseline	4.1 (0.0090)	20.6 (0.0454)	12.3 (0.0272)	7.5 (0.0164)	0.78 (22.08)
J3022 Test 2 MAHLE Near Net Shape Steel	3.5 (0.0078)	11.5 (0.0254)	7.5 (0.0166)	5.22 (0.0115)	0.71 (20.25)

Table 4: Oil Consumption & Blowby Comparison With Micro Vs. Nano Napier Ring

4.3 Benchmarking

The evolution of ring designs has been marked by progress towards more efficient configurations. The latest Nano Napier steel design has demonstrated outstanding performance in oil consumption tests. Notably, the tension of the Nano Napier Ring does not exceed that of other alternatives, yet it delivers superior results. With blowby rates lower than those of other designs and no changes made to pistons and top rings, the Nano Napier design stands out for its effectiveness without the need for increased tension.

Table 5: Oil Consumption & Blowby Comparison With Micro Vs. Nano Napier Ring

The supplier has been delivering a diverse array of original North American equipment programs with the NNSi (Nano-Napier) steel ring design since 2014, covering a broad range of ring sizes from 79 to 107 mm. These rings are employed in engines with various configurations, including two rings for inline-4 engines, one for V6 engines, and two for V8 engines. It is worth noting that in the 2020 model year, one of the six NNSi programs is shifting towards a chrome-free NNSi design for the outer-diameter coating, whereas the other five programs will continue to incorporate the chrome plate for the ring's outer diameter coating.

The extensive Proof of Concept (POC) testing, coupled with thorough benchmarking, has considerably heightened confidence in the proposed nano-Napier ring design. This has paved the way for the additional examination of this design as a viable means of achieving technical cost reduction within manufacturing procedures.

4.4 DFMEA

An essential aspect of promoting the idea of using a nano-Napier ring design involves conducting a thorough Design Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (DFMEA). This assessment enables a more profound comprehension of potential failure modes and their consequences as well as the design controls, detection methods, and validation processes necessary for a smooth transition to the nano-Napier option. It is imperative that we address these areas comprehensively to ensure successful and effective implementation of the nano-Napier alternative.

Potential Failure Mode	Potential Effects of failure	Sev	Potential cause of failure	Occ	Current Design Controls-Detection	Det	RPN
Broken Ring Improper side seal	Loss of Power (6) Smoke from Tail Pipe (5) High Oil Consumption (6) Oil Fouled Air Cleaner (5) Lack of Performance (6) Increased emissions (10) Improper oil control Corrosion (rust) on parts	10	Improper base material selection Inadequate gap @ gage (ring butting) Excessive side wear Oversressed at installation Insufficient corrosion protection Damage during assembly Insufficient side clearance Ring face scuff Improper Ring face finish Incorrect gap @ gage Improper ring tension Ring flutter Piston scuff Dirt ingestion during operation Dirt from engine assembly Improper lube oil Inadequate PCV flow Incorrect calibration Excessive fuel delivery Improper face coating Insufficient heat transfer Carbon build up in napier Piston groove collapse Ring hot stick Excessive carbon in groove Bore distortion & Bore finish Bore over sized or under sized Piston groove finish Piston groove inclination Excess temperature Improper base ring material Microwelding Ring waviness Piston groove waviness Poor ring pack dynamic	3	Dynamometer durability testing: DTS(Deep Thermal Shock Test), GED (Gasoline Engine Durability Test), FEE(Fire Engine Endurance Test), ERES (Engine Resonance Survey Test), and PTTRANS. Vehicle durability testing: PTDS, Mechanical Development Testing: Hot scuff, Cold scuff, Bench Testing: Skirt fatigue, Crown fatigue, Pin boss fatigue, Thermal fatigue, Land fatigue, Windowed piston on engine back to verify proper flow, Strain Measurements, Performance Testing per Engine Performance Test Procedures, Vehicle durability testing	3	90

Table 6: Piston DFMEA for nano-Napier

Potential Failure Mode	Potential Effects of failure	Sev	Potential cause of failure	Occ	Current Design Controls-Detection	Det	RPN
Improper oil control	Loss of Power (6) Smoke from Tail Pipe (5) High Oil Consumption (6) Oil Fouled Air Cleaner (5) Lack of Performance (8) Increased emissions (10) Improper oil control Corrosion (rust) on parts	10	Insufficient corrosion protection Insufficient side clearance Improper Ring side surface finish Ring flutter Dirt ingestion during operation Dirt from engine assembly Improper lube oil maintenance Inadequate PC flow Incorrect calibration Excessive fuel delivery	3	Dynamometer durability testing: DTS (Deep Thermal Shock Test), GED (Gasoline Engine Durability Test), FEE (Fire Engine Endurance Test), ERS (Engine Resonance Survey Test), and PT2TRANS. Vehicle durability testing: PT2/3. Mechanical Development Testing: Hot scuff, Cold scuff, Bench Testing: Skirt fatigue, Crown fatigue, Pin boss fatigue, Thermal fatigue, Land fatigue, Windowed piston on engine back to verify proper flow, Strain Measurements, Performance Testing per Engine Performance Test Procedures, Vehicle durability testing	4	120
Corrosion (rust) on parts		10	Inadequate coating material for corrosion protection, scuff resistance, and wear.	2		2	40
Failure to assemble	Excessive Down-Time during Assembly (5) Excessive Labor Operation (LOP) Costs during Service (5)	10	Piston, ring & bore interference during assembly Inadequate lubrication of cylinder bore prior to stuffing Improper material selection	3	Engine Assy Control Plan Teardown inspection after PCM stuffing comparing witness marks to historical norms.	3	90

Table 7: Piston DFMEA for nano-Napier

The Design Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (DFMEA) identified four primary failure modes: a broken ring improper side seal, improper oil control, corrosion of parts, and failure to assemble. These failures could result in significant consequences, including loss of power, smoke from the tailpipe, high oil consumption, oil fouled air cleaner, lack of performance, increased emissions, and improper oil control corrosion rust on the parts. These failures may be caused by various factors, such as improper base material selection, inadequate gaps causing ring butting, excessive side wear, overstress at installation, insufficient corrosion protection, damage during assembly, insufficient side clearance ring face scuff, improper ring face finish, incorrect gap @ gage, improper ring tension, ring flutter, piston scuff, dirt ingestion during operation, dirt from engine assembly, improper lube oil, inadequate PCV flow, incorrect calibration, excessive fuel delivery, improper face coating, insufficient heat transfer, carbon build-up in the Napier, piston groove collapse, ring hot stuck, excessive carbon in the groove, bore distortion and bore finish, bore oversized or undersized piston groove finish, piston groove waviness, excess temperature, improper base ring material, micro-welding ring waviness, piston groove waviness, and poor ring pack dynamics. These failure points received high severity ratings, leading to significant Risk Priority Number (RPN) scores, emphasizing the importance of addressing these issues during the design and validation phases.

4.5 DVPR

To identify and prevent potential issues, such as a damaged piston ring, improper side seal, corroded components, and incorrect assembly, it is recommended to conduct a range of tests, including general durability evaluations, peak power assessments, and scuff resistance trials. To diagnose oil consumption problems, the use of Lubrisense steady-state and transient tests for dyno-test engines is recommended. Additionally, standardized city and highway driving cycles should be employed during vehicle testing to confirm that the vehicle-level oil consumption is not adversely affected. These measures were implemented to ensure comprehensive detection and protection against wear-related failures.

4.6 General Durability Test

An approach involving a series of phases was implemented to evaluate potential cost savings. The initial step involved conducting a preliminary durability test to gauge the impact of the proposed adjustments and facilitating a targeted assessment prior to dedicating the entire budget for further testing.

Figure 10: Piston #6 Ring Groove Trace

Figure 11: Piston #4 Ring Groove Trace

Considering the substantial wear visible on the ring grooves, the proposed switch to non-hard-anodized (non-HA) grooves was placed on-hold. Although nano-Napier modification and chrome removal did not raise any concerns regarding the functionality of the parts, the anticipated financial savings were not sufficient to justify the expenses associated with testing. Consequently, it was determined that implementing these changes as stand-alone modifications would not be cost-effective.

5. Conclusion

Investigations into the technical cost reduction strategies for the 3.6 L V6 engine reveal that while certain modifications, such as the nano-Napier design show promise in terms of performance and potential cost savings, others, such as the removal of anodizing on the piston top ring groove, may not be feasible owing to increased wear risks. This study highlights the importance of comprehensive testing and analysis, including DFMEA and DVPR assessments, to validate proposed changes. Moving forward, the findings suggest a cautious approach to implementing cost-reduction measures, prioritizing the engine's long-term reliability and functionality to ensure that any modifications contribute positively to both operational efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

6. Future Work

Future studies should focus on conducting long-term durability trials to evaluate the impact of removing the anodized layer from the piston top ring groove by monitoring wear and performance over an extended period and various conditions. Additionally, exploring alternative coating materials, such as advanced ceramics and diamond-like carbon (DLC) coatings, may offer similar or improved wear resistance, enhancing performance and cost-effectiveness. Refining the nano-Napier ring design, including a thorough analysis and optimization of ring geometry and material properties, is crucial for maximizing oil control, minimizing blow-by, and improving overall engine efficiency. Real-world field testing in diverse conditions will provide valuable data on performance, durability, and customer satisfaction, ensuring that the proposed modifications meet industry requirements. The use of advanced diagnostic tools and techniques, such as real-time wear monitoring and predictive maintenance technologies, will facilitate close monitoring of engine components, allowing for early issue detection and optimized maintenance schedules. Lastly, a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis, considering direct and indirect costs, potential savings, and the impacts on engine performance and customer satisfaction, is necessary to validate the feasibility of the proposed modifications.

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Definitions/Abbreviations

NVH: Noise Vibration Harshness

CAE: Computer Aided Engineering

RCA: Root Cause Analysis

POC: Proof of Concept

WOT: Wide Open Throttle

Dyno: Dynamometer

DFMEA: Design Failure Mode and Effects Analysis

DVPR: Design Verification Plan and Report

HA: Hard Anodizing

µm: Micrometers

COE: Center of Excellence

OD: Outer Diameter

NNSi: Nano-Napier Steel Ring

DI: Direct Injection

GED: General Engine Durability

PCV: Positive Crankcase Ventilation

DLC: Diamond-Like Carbon